

HSF Technical Notes policy

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Abstract

The note describes the HSF Technical Notes policy, the rationale behind the notes series, and further recommendations. This is the first version of the policy for the HEP Software Foundation (HSF) Technical Notes series, and itself serves as an example technical note.

1 Introduction

This is the first version of the policy for the HEP Software Foundation (HSF) Technical Notes series, and itself serves as an example technical note.

The technical notes series provides an early example of community level co-operation and interoperation that can be fostered by HSF. It is hoped that groups of projects will co-operate on writing notes for interfaces they provide or use, and HSF will offer support and publicity for any meetings and workshops that result from these collaborative efforts.

The notes series provides archived, numbered documents that can be referenced in software documentation and papers, and the notes themselves may also become the basis for papers associated with HSF member projects.

2 Policies

1. HSF technical notes are informational, and they do not constitute standards or recommendations.
2. If a note needs to describe the required and optional elements of an interface between systems, then use of the conventional key words “MUST”, “MUST NOT”, “REQUIRED”, “SHALL”, “SHALL NOT”, “SHOULD”, “SHOULD NOT”, “RECOMMENDED”, “MAY”, and “OPTIONAL” as described in RFC 2119 [?] is preferred.
3. HSF limits its editorial input to checking that the document is within the scope of HSF, and has the required format, grammar, and spelling.
4. HSF avoids attempting to judge whether the subject matter of a proposed technical note is sufficiently significant or not. Acceptance of a technical note does not constitute an endorsement of its contents or importance.
5. A simple format for notes will be provided as a LaTeX template, but technical notes must be supplied by authors as PDF files. Any method for creating a PDF file in a similar format is acceptable, such as Word or Pages as a substitute for LaTeX.
6. The copyright of a technical note remains with its authors, but the note must be made available with a Creative Commons Attribution license, CC-BY-4.0 or later.
7. Notes which have been produced as reports for other purposes may be accepted in PDF form as HSF technical notes provided the title page of the submitted PDF file conforms to the HSF format including the assigned HSF identifier, and the entire document is made available under the above Creative Commons license.
8. An archive of technical notes will be made available on a website managed by HSF.
9. Each technical note will be assigned an identifier of the format HSF-TN-YYYY-NN when it is finally accepted and archived by HSF. Notes should be referenced as

Author(s), HSF-TN-YYYY-NN “The Title” (HEP Software Foundation) rather than with a URL.

10. Once published, substantive revisions to the technical note will not be accepted. This is similar to the IETF RFC model [?].
11. Subsequent notes may be accepted covering updates to the same subject matter and a new note identifier will be issued. Projects are encouraged to give version numbers to their interfaces to clarify the process of documenting their interfaces as they evolve over time. HSF may prefix copies of older notes presented on the archive website with forward references to newer versions.

3 Procedure

Draft technical notes should be submitted following the process published in the Technical Notes section of the HSF website. The acceptance process will be managed by editors for the HSF Technical Notes series appointed by the HSF governing body (initially, by the HSF interim Foundation Board). The series editors may co-opt other people to act as additional editors for a given technical note. The editorial process will include at least one week of consultation on the proposed final draft within the HSF community.

4 Recommendations

HSF working groups are asked to work towards producing technical notes which record their outcomes.

Interested projects or groups of projects are encouraged to suggest technical notes documenting their interfaces and methods. It is likely that many projects have documents like this already (e.g. as wiki pages, sections of published papers or PhD theses) that can readily be reworked and perhaps expanded into technical notes.

5 Standards

If there is a need for HSF to manage standards, then a procedure will be developed for endorsing suitable technical notes as standards documents.

6 Summary

This technical note sets out the rationale, policies, and recommendations for further HSF technical notes.

References

- [1] S. Bradner, RFC2119 “Key words for use in RFCs to Indicate Requirement Levels” (Internet Engineering Task Force)
- [2] S. Bradner, RFC2026 “The Internet Standards Process – Revision 3” (Internet Engineering Task Force)